

Recommended citation: Rützou, C. (2017). Active Learning in Practice: Implementation of the Principles of Active Learning in an Engineering Course . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 1451-1458). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698585.

Active Learning in Practice

Implementation of the principles of Active Learning in an engineering course

C. Rützou

Associate Professor
Technical University of Denmark (DTU)
Ballerup, Denmark
E-mail: carru@dtu.dk

ABSTRACT

The most common form of teaching is still the form where a teacher presents the subject of the lecture to a listening audience. During teaching history this has proved to be an effective way of teaching, however the probability of students being inactive is high and the learning outcome may be small for these students.

An alternative teaching method is “Active Learning” and in the autumn 2015 we implemented this method to a 5 ects. course of “Material Science”. What we wanted to examine was:

- How can Active Learning be implemented in the Material Science course
- Is it possible to get through the same curriculum as usual during a term?
- Will Active Learning reduce failure rate?
- Will Active Learning give a higher learning outcome than traditional teaching?

This paper deals with the results of this experiment, answers the mentioned questions and presents a way to implement Active Learning.

INTRODUCTION

In the spring 2015 the subject of the biannual teaching and learning seminar which The Technical University of Denmark (DTU) arranged had the subject “Active Learning”.

The main speaker at the seminar was Mark Decker¹⁾ who gave an excellent presentation of the principles of Active Learning under the title “The One Who Does the Work Does the Learning”.

We decided to implement the ideas of Active Learning in my course; a 1st semester course for diploma engineering students with the subject: Materials Science.

The subjects of my study were:

- How can we implement the model of Active Learning in the Materials Science course?
- Is it possible to get through the same curriculum as usual during a term?
- Will our implementation of Active Learning reduce failure rate?
- Will our implementation of Active Learning give a higher learning outcome than traditional teaching?

The project of implementing the Active Learning principles in the course was succeeded in the autumn 2015, and after this semester Active Learning has been conducted three times.

1 ACTIVE LEARNING AND TEACHER CONTROLLED TEACHING

1.1 The One Who Does the Work Does the Learning

The basic idea behind Active Learning is that the outcome of learning is higher for a student who reads the text, works with the exercises and tries to find solutions to the problems rather than a student who gets the curriculum told by a teacher and sees the solutions to exercises on a screen before having worked with them.

That is what is behind the words: 'The One Who Does the Work Does the Learning'. When one reads the lecture material and then works with the problems given in the text or as an appendix to the text and try to understand difficult parts by working with them instead of just asking an expert, the learning outcome will be high.

So the basic principle behind Active Learning, as a structure in the lessons, is that the teacher does not speak or present the curriculum, instead the students use the time to make self-studying. This can be in groups or individually, but in most cases group work is used.

1.2 Mark Decker's structure of a lesson based on Active Learning

One of the basic principles in Mark Decker's¹⁾ implementation of Active Learning is group work and here it is important that the facilities of the tuition room(s), support group work. Actually a sub title to the teaching and learning seminar at DTU in the spring 2015 was "Creating Effective Active Learning Environments" and here a room with small tables and many whiteboards was suggested.

The structure of the lesson is an alternation between group work with problems given by the teacher and group presentations of the results from the group work.

Mark Decker divides the curriculum of the day into the levels of Bloom's Taxonomy. The part of the curriculum of the day which belongs to the lower levels of Bloom's Taxonomy is not discussed in the lecture. It is taken for granted that the students have made themselves acquainted with this part, which can be read from a text book or from other sources. "The students always meet up well prepared" Mark Decker claims and if they do not, they will soon learn that if they are to perform in the group, they have to be well prepared.

The questions, which are discussed and later presented by the groups, start from or just above level 2 and during the lesson climb higher and higher and sometimes, reach top level.

The students are active throughout the lesson either by working with the problems, by presenting their results or by evaluating other groups' work. The groups that are to present their results are chosen from a random number generator, so the groups have the same probability for being selected for presentations and therefore they quickly learn to utilize the group working time efficiently. A point system ensures that the students actually do the group work and don't let the person who seems to be the most clever answers the questions.

The active work in the class room and the active acquisition of the basic stuff at home ensures the Active Learning.

1.3 The Traditional Teaching method and the Active Learning

It is often mentioned that Active Learning (and many other teaching methods) gives a higher learning outcome than the widely used method where a person tells and presents subjects to students. However, when alternative teaching methods such as 'Problem Based Learning', 'Learning by Inquiry', 'Spiral learning', 'Learning with Cases' are presented, it is often where the amount of "subjects" or the complexity

isn't high. In many courses with higher complexity or where the amount of details to be acquainted with is high, the teacher often selects the teaching method where he or she presents the stuff to the students.

In situations where textbooks and other sources are not in good agreement with the content of the course, the teacher also often selects teacher controlled teaching.

Teacher controlled teaching still has some advantages and there may also be students who learn more from an expert than from self-studies and group discussions.

The course Material Science is a course with high complexity and a high amount of details. Therefore this course was selected as test course.

2 IMPLEMENTATION OF ACTIVE LEARNING IN THE MATERIAL SCIENCE COURSE.

2.1 The planned structure

The following lesson structure was decided as a practical bridge between the recommendations of Mark Decker¹⁾ and what seemed feasible.

0:00 - 0:30 Class discussions of questions which the students have asked me to go through after the previous lesson. Questions can be given after the previous lesson or during the week.

0:30 – 0:45 Presentation of the subject of the day and presentation of the questions they have to work with in groups.

0:45 – 1:45 The students work in groups with the questions

1:45 – 2:00 The groups present their work and their answers to the questions

2:00 – 2:10 Collection of questions to be highlighted next time.

2:10 – 4:00 Half of the groups work with exercises (standard home exercises) which are to be handed in 7 or 14 days later. The other half of the groups work with practical exercises in a material test laboratory. Over each of these exercises the groups shall deliver a journal. The groups alternate such that next week the group working with the home exercises will make the practical exercises and vice versa.

As can be seen each lecture covers four hours, where the final two consist of some kind of exercise.

The material the students have to read before the lecture is certain pages in the text book and the power points I would have used during a normal lesson.

Before the experiment started in the autumn 2015, the final two hours of the 4 hour lesson were also reserved for exercises and one can claim that in this period the students did a kind of Active Learning, however it is not in accordance with the definition of Active Learning.

When comparing with the Active Learning as presented by Mark Decker, it is seen that the full model of Active Learning is not implemented. *First* each lesson starts with half an hour of teacher treated content, however this part of the stuff is an enquiry from some students and it is assumed that the students are motivated to actively follow the teacher's explanations. *Second* the questions given are based on the textbook and the notes which the students have been able to download from our information board at least a week in advance. So the questions and discussion deals with the lowest level of Bloom's taxonomy.

There were three reasons for this model.

- The students are newly enrolled in the university and have no experience in studying. For many of the students the jump from being guided through the material to be an active student is high.
- Although being an experiment the demand; that the experiment must not result in lower exam grades or in lower learning outcome has not been reduced, thus I did not dare to make too large a step.
- The experiment should reveal the above mentioned effects from Active Learning. Therefore I did not dare to change to many parameters at a time. The job was to investigate the effects of exchanging the speaking teacher with self-studying groups.

2.2 The structure as it developed

Active Learning was introduced in the first lecture in order to make it start from lecture no. 2. And the model from above was introduced.

1. It soon became clear that the session with groups presenting the results they had achieved during group work did not work. I had not implemented the random number generator or the point system, which might have helped. Some groups declined presenting their results, and soon it was the same two groups that presented their results each time.

Often they had some difficulties answering the questions which gave me an opportunity to address these questions to the auditory and thereby start a class discussion over a subject which assumable all groups had had problems with. However this does not violate the principles in Active Learning, so I did not make any efforts in changing this.

Another problem was the time schedule. Only 15 minutes were reserved for the presentation/discussion part of the lecture and this was not enough. Often we finished the theoretical part of the lesson after 2½ hours giving only 1½ hour for exercises.

These problems caused that group presentations over a period of about two months stopped and were fully replaced with class discussions.

2. A problem, which quickly rose, was that the students felt uncertain whether they learned what they had to. Many people have the feeling that what they learn through self-study is not as good as what a professional teacher can teach them. It makes Active Learning an insecure experience.

In the course description 8 to 12 learning objectives are given, this is sufficient for a student to select or deselect the course or for a board to get an impression of the course content. But for a student, who follows the course, these learning objectives are insufficient to use as indicators for how well their learning complies with what is expected.

So in order to give the students indicators they can use to evaluate how well they follow the course, I made a list of learning objectives for each lesson. The number of learning objectives for each lesson was between 8 and 12 and the complete list ended with about 100 learning objectives. This list proved to be a great help giving the students a feedback of how well they followed the expected learning outcome.

I named the list '*Core Elements*', ignoring that this concept is often used for other subjects in the teaching environment.

3. After a while the students stopped making question to be treated the following lesson. The reason was not that they had a good understanding of all the questions and felt secure regarding that. The reason was partly that some lost their overview over weak subjects, some were not able to express their questions and others were not so worried over what they did not understand that they formulated it as a problem to go through.

Therefore I got the idea to start each lesson with the list of core elements from the previous lesson and use this as a check list. For each core element I asked the auditorium whether they felt that they had an adequate understanding of the subject, or if they knew how to achieve this understanding. This helped a lot for revealing soft spots.

The planned half hour was often insufficient for teaching these subjects; however it also turned out that it was unnecessary with 15 minutes for presenting the subject of the day, so some time was taken from this activity.

At the end of the course the daily plan had changed to:

0:00 - 0:40 Showing and discussing the core elements from the previous lesson on the video projector screen. Making a short teaching/updating of the subjects where the students wants a deeper understanding, however in order not to start to much ordinary teaching, the discussion is made without PowerPoint support. Mostly oral explanations and some strokes on the whiteboard

0:40 – 0:45 Presentation of the subject of the day and presentation of the questions they have to work with in groups.

0:45 – 1:45 The students work in groups with the questions.

1:45 – 2:20 Class discussion of the answers to the mentioned questions.

2:25 – 4:00 Half of the groups work with exercises (standard home exercises) to be handed in 7 or 14 days later. The other half of the groups work with practical exercises in a material test laboratory. Over each of these exercises the groups must write a journal.

Despite changing the ideal lesson plan it is still Active Learning, because the achievement and treatment of the new learning subjects are done by themselves, I only help when they need help.

3 DID THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ACTIVE LEARNING GIVE AN ANSWER ON THE MENTIONED SUBJECTS?

3.1 How can Active Learning be implemented in the material science course?

In part 2.1 and 2.2 above a course structure utilising the ideas of Active Learning is described. The plan follow the suggestions of Mark Decker¹⁾ with the following exceptions:

- In the first 30 to 40 minutes of the lectures the core elements from the previous lesson are discussed. Partly as repetition but mostly as a check for the student to clarify, whether their knowledge of the stuff is adequate or need further treatment.
- The questions in the self-study time belong to the lowest level of Bloom's Taxonomy, where Mark Decker recommends that they deal with the higher levels.
- There were no score systems for the students and the presentation session was replaced with an open class discussion.

3.2 Is it possible to get through the same curriculum as usual during a term?

Yes, we came through the same amount of material as in the previous semesters. The distribution of the curriculum over the lessons was exactly the same. In a way it was easier, because the students got the whole curriculum for the day to read and to get acquainted with and there was no expectation that the questions they worked with did cover the entire curriculum, but they should still adopt the stuff.

In a normal lesson it is expected that the teacher gets through all the stuff that has been given in the curriculum of the day.

3.3 Will our implementation of Active Learning reduce the failure rate?

Figure 1. The Danish ECTS grade levels.

ECTS Grade	Description
A	Excellent
B	Very good
C	Good
D	Average
E	Sufficient
Fx	Insufficient
F	Poor

The course ends with a 4 hours' written exam, and the above mentioned question is best answered through a study of the examination results which are sorted into the levels shown in figure 1.

Figures 2A and 2B show the examination scores and only students who participate in the exams for the first time are included.

Figure 2A. Scores for the 3 first semesters

The semesters with teacher conducted teaching gave the following failure rates: 0.21, 0.30 and 0.09 giving a mean of 0.20 and a standard deviation of 0.102

The semesters with Active Learning gave the following failure rates: 0.0, 0.13 and 0.04 giving a mean of 0.06 and a standard deviation of 0.066

The failure rates and the calculated mean values are shown in figure 3.A

A mean failure rate of just 0.06 contra 0.2 indicates that Active Learning gives a lower failure rate but it is interesting to calculate how significant this deviation is.

Due to the poor statistical material it is supposed that the mean values follow a Student-T distribution which is shown in figure 3.B.

Figure 2B. Scores for the 3 last semesters

The true mean failure rate for teacher conducted teaching is called μ_C and the mean failure rate for Active Learning is called μ_A . The question to be answered is: Based on the given data, on which confidence level is μ_A is lower than μ_C ?

By utilizing the student-T test it can be calculated that $\mu_C > 0.11$ on an 85 % confidence level.

$$\mu_{C, \text{lower bound}} = 0.20 + T.INV(1 - 0.85, 2) \cdot 0.102 / \sqrt{3} > 0.11$$

And it can be calculated that $\mu_A < 0.11$ on a 85% confidence level:

$$\mu_{A, \text{upper bound}} = 0.06 + T.INV(0.85, 2) \cdot 0.066 / \sqrt{3} < 0.11$$

where $T.INV(\alpha, \beta)$ is the invers cumulated Student T distribution with probability α and degree of freedom β .

I.e. the data shows a significantly lower mean failure rate for Active Learning on a confidence level 85 %. ($\mu_{C, \text{lower bound}} > \mu_{A, \text{upper bound}}$).

Figure 3A. Measured failure rates and calculated mean values

Figure 3B. Mean failure rates follow a T-distribution

3.4 Will our implementation of Active Learning give a higher learning outcome than traditional teaching?

With the concept "Learning Outcome", I mean the deep understanding or the academic insight that lies well beyond "just passing the exam", where one can understand why the elements are designed and why they have the properties they have or in other words; the knowledge where one gets to the top three levels of Bloom's taxonomy.

A good question is whether there are measurements that can reveal whether the proportion of students, who have achieved this goal, has risen?

One could suggest that the fraction of passed students who achieve a C, B or A, or perhaps just the fraction of students who has obtained a B or A, indicates the fraction of students who have reached a level of deep understanding. An increase in these fractions in the Active Learning semesters could indicate that Active Learning gives deeper learning outcome.

The fraction of students having passed the examination and obtained a C, B or A score can be calculated as:

$$F_{ABC} = \frac{F_A + F_B + F_C}{F_A + F_B + F_C + F_D + F_E} = \frac{\text{Fraction A, B and C}}{(\text{Fraction A, B and C}) + (\text{Fraction D and E})}$$

where F_A is the fraction of students in the class who obtained an A, F_B is the fraction of students in the class who obtained a B, and so on. (Fraction A, B and C) and (Fraction D and E) can be read from tables below figure 2A and 2B.

Similarly, the fraction of students having passed the examination and obtained an B or A score can be calculated as:

$$F_{AB} = \frac{F_A + F_B}{F_A + F_B + F_C + F_D + F_E} = \frac{\text{Fraction A and B}}{(\text{Fraction A, B and C}) + (\text{Fraction D and E})}$$

The mean value for F_{ABC} in the years with traditional teaching is: 0.62

The mean value for F_{ABC} in the years with Active Learning is: 0.59

Which must be interpreted as; “no difference” compared with the scattering of the results.

The mean value for F_{AB} in the years with traditional teaching is: 0.39

The mean value for F_{AB} in the years with Active Learning is: 0.33

Which again must be interpreted as; “no difference” compared with the scattering of the results.

So the test does not indicate that Active Learning gives an achievement of deep understanding, nor the opposite. (The two numbers are a bit lower for the years with Active Learning, but due to the scattering of the results this must be interpreted as random deviations).

4 CONCLUSION

A pedagogical experiment of using Active Learning as replacement of the traditional teaching was conducted with the purpose of answering the following questions:

- How can we implement the model of Active Learning in the Materials Science course? *The study showed that this was possible.*
- Is it possible to get through the same curriculum as usual during a term? *Yes*
- Will our implementation of Active Learning reduce the failure rate? *Yes. Data shows that Active Learning gives lower failure rates on a confidence level of 85 %*
- Will our implementation of Active Learning give a higher learning outcome than traditional teaching? *No it is unaltered.*

REFERENCES

- [1] Decker, Mark, Teaching Associate Professor, University of Minnesota. Seminar at DTU: “The One Who Does the Work Does the Learning: Creating Effective Active Learning Environments”. 17th of March 2015